

Phytochemical Profiling and GC-MS Analysis of *Pleurotus ostreatus* (Oyster mushroom) Obtained in Lagos, Nigeria

Oloyede, M. Adeola^{1*}, and Worship O. Agbonifo²

¹Department of Cell Biology and Genetics, University of Lagos, Akoka, Lagos-Nigeria.

²Department of Physiology, Federal University of Technology, Akure, Ondo-Nigeria.

*Correspondence: moloyede@unilag.edu.ng; +2348022215162

Submission: 24th October., 2025; Accepted: 2nd November, 2025; Published: 30th November, 2025

Abstract

Pleurotus ostreatus is an edible mushroom valued for its nutritional richness and therapeutic potential, largely attributed to its diverse phytochemical constituents. This study aimed to characterize the phytochemical makeup and proximate composition of *P. ostreatus* using qualitative and quantitative assays together with gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC-MS). Ethanolic extracts of oven-dried mushroom samples were subjected to standard phytochemical and proximate assays, while GC–MS analysis was applied to detect and characterize the bioactive constituents. The extract tested positive for alkaloids, tannins, saponins, terpenoids, cardiac glycosides, steroids, reducing sugars, flavonoids, and phenols, with saponins occurring in the highest concentration (52.50 mg/100 g). Proximate analysis revealed high levels of protein (31.15 %) and crude fiber (37.02 %), alongside low fat content (0.097 %), indicating substantial nutritional value. GC–MS profiling identified twenty-nine compounds, including 2(5H)-Furanone, 3-methyl-, L-arabinitol, Bromoacetic acid octadecyl ester, 9,17-Octadecadienal (Z)-, and Didodecyl phthalate, metabolites associated with antioxidant, antimicrobial, and cytoprotective properties. The findings suggest that *P. ostreatus* is an abundant source of bioactive and nutritionally beneficial compounds, capable of supporting human health through multiple biochemical mechanisms. The findings affirm the mushroom’s role as a functional food and natural reservoir of therapeutic agents, underscoring its potential for use in nutraceutical and pharmaceutical applications.

Keywords: Bioactive compounds, functional food, GC–MS analysis, phytochemical profiling, *Pleurotus ostreatus*.

1.0 Introduction

Mushrooms are soft, spore-producing reproductive structures of fungi that commonly emerge in forested and agricultural habitats after rainfall, grow to sizes easily visible, and are harvested manually [1;2]. They typically emerge above the ground, either directly on soil or on their nutrient source such as putrefying wood or other organic substrate, and they favour moist, cool environments for fruit body formation [2]. Species of the genus *Pleurotus* are saprophytes that derive growth nutrients via mycelium penetrating and absorbing nutrients from substrate [3;4].

Pleurotus ostreatus (Oyster mushroom) is particularly notable for its nutritional and medicinal value [5]. It is widely cultivated because of its ability to grow on diverse agricultural wastes and its high yield of protein-rich food [5]. These mushroom supplies protein of high nutritional quality, together with dietary fibre and various micronutrients, making it a valuable meat alternative in functional foods [6]. Research has also documented its anti-diabetic, anti-hypertensive, and anti-inflammatory activities, supporting its use in traditional medicine [7;8]. These therapeutic properties are largely attributed to its phytochemical profile, which includes phenolic acids, flavonoids, terpenes, and other secondary metabolites that can scavenge free

radicals and modulate biochemical pathways [7]. Phytochemical profiling of edible mushrooms is therefore important to understand the bioactive compounds responsible for their nutraceutical potential [9]. Common phytochemicals in mushrooms may contribute to antioxidant, antimicrobial, and other pharmacological effects [9]. Identifying these constituents, both qualitatively and quantitatively, will provide further insight into how *P. ostreatus* may be developed as a functional food ingredient and as a natural source of therapeutic agents [9].

Furthermore, gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC–MS) provides an efficient analytical technique for characterizing volatile and semi-volatile compounds in plant and fungal extracts [10]. The application of GC–MS to *P. ostreatus* therefore provides a robust means of profiling its diverse bioactive constituents, enhancing understanding of its nutritional, medicinal, and functional benefits [11]. This study aimed at investigating and providing a comprehensive pharmacognostic analysis of *P. ostreatus* with respect to its phytochemical constituents, GC–MS identification of its chemical compounds, showing the full spectrum of bioactive and nutritional components.

2.0. Materials and Methods

2.1. Sample Collection

Indigenous mushroom species, *Pleurotus ostreatus* were collected in June 2025, from the mushroom bank at the Federal Institute of Industrial Research, Oshodi, Lagos State. The samples were identified at the herbarium unit of Department of Botany, University of Lagos, Akoka with voucher number LUH100639.

2.2. Sample Preparation and Extraction

Dried mushroom was blended into powder form using Jd SMP Je-01 blender. Crude extraction was done by soaking 1500 g of powdered *P. ostreatus* fruit bodies in 7000 ml of absolute ethanol. The containers were sealed with aluminum foil and allowed to stand for 72 hours at room temperature with intermittent agitation. Filtration was performed using a cotton wool–packed funnel to derive clear filtrate free of particulate matter. The filtrate (6200 mL), was concentrated under reduced pressure at $40 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ to yield 98 g of dark

brown extract. The dried extract was stored at 4°C in airtight universal bottles for pharmacognostic studies.

2.3. Phytochemical Screening

The ethanolic extract of *Pleurotus ostreatus* was subjected to qualitative phytochemical screening for secondary metabolites such as alkaloids [12], tannins, phenols, flavonoids and saponins [13], terpenoids [14], cardiac glycosides and steroids [15], reducing sugars, amino acids and carbohydrates [16].

2.4. Proximate Analysis

The proximate of powdered mushrooms were studied for crude protein, moisture, volatile matter, fixed carbon and ash on a mass percent basis. The analyses were carried out following the procedures described by the Association of official Analytical Chemists [17].

2.5. GAS Chromatography–Mass Spectrometry

GC–MS analysis of the ethanolic extract was carried out on an Agilent 5977B GC/MSD system fitted with an Agilent 8860 autosampler. Separation was achieved on an Elite-5MS fused-silica capillary column (30 m \times 0.25 mm i.d., 0.25 μm film thickness; 5% diphenyl/95% dimethylpolysiloxane stationary phase) [18]. The instrument operated in electron-impact ionization mode at 70 eV. Helium (99.999%) was used as the carrier gas at a constant flow rate of 1.0 mL/min. A 1 μL aliquot of the sample was injected in split mode (split ratio 10:1), with the injector temperature set at 300°C and the ion source at 250°C [18]. The oven program started at 100°C (held for 0.5 min), then increased at $20^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ to 280°C , followed by a final hold of 2.5 min. Mass spectra were recorded over an m/z range of 45–450 with a scan time of 0.5 s and a solvent delay of 0–3 min, giving a total run time of 20 min. Compound identification was based on comparison of the acquired spectra with entries in the NIST mass spectral library [18].

2.6. Statistical Analysis

The data obtained were entered into the excel sheet and Mean \pm SD was calculated using Microsoft Excel 2010 for Windows.

3.0. Results

3.1. Phytochemical Composition of *Pleurotus ostreatus*

Qualitative Phytochemical Profile

As shown in Table 1, qualitative screening of the ethanolic extract of *Pleurotus ostreatus* revealed the presence of alkaloids, terpenoids, tannins, cardiac glycosides, saponins, steroids, reducing sugars, flavonoids and phenolic compounds, while phlobatannins were absent. Among the detected compounds, saponins were present in high abundance.

Table 1: Phytochemicals detected in the Ethanolic Extract of *Pleurotus ostreatus*

Phytochemical Constituents	Presence
Alkaloid	+
Tannin	+
Phlobatannin	-
Saponin	++
Terpenoid	+
Cardiac Glycosides	+
Steroid	+
Reducing Sugar	+
Flavonoid	+
Phenol	+

+ = Present, ++ = Much in abundance, - = Absent

Quantitative Estimation of Phytochemicals

The mean concentrations (mg/100 g) and standard deviations of the phytochemical constituents identified in the extract are presented in Table 2. The measured levels were 42.73 ± 0.44 for alkaloids, 37.5 ± 0.56 for tannins, 52.50 ± 0.02 for saponins, 36.88 ± 0.59 for terpenoids, 30.27 ± 0.06 for cardiac glycosides, 24.29 ± 0.06 for steroids, 29.63 ± 0.01 for reducing sugars, 42.27 ± 0.04 for flavonoids, and 46.52 ± 0.66 for phenols.

3.2. Proximate Composition of *Pleurotus ostreatus*

Table 3 presents the proximate composition of *Pleurotus ostreatus*. The mushroom sample contained 17.54% moisture, 10.82% ash, 0.097% fat, 37.02% crude fiber, 31.15% protein, and 3.373% nitrogen-free extract (NFE) carbohydrate

content. The carbohydrate content determined by the Anthrone method was 2.575 g/100 g.

Table 2: Levels of Phytochemicals in the Ethanolic Extract of *Pleurotus ostreatus*

Phytochemicals	Levels (mg/100 g)
Alkaloid	42.73±0.44
Tannin	37.56±0.56
Saponin	52.50±0.02
Terpenoid	36.88±0.59
Cardiac Glycosides	30.27±0.06
Steroid	24.29±0.06
Reducing Sugar	29.63±0.01
Flavonoid	42.27±0.04
Phenol	46.52±0.66

Values are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (mg/100 g).

Table 3: Proximate Composition of *Pleurotus ostreatus*

Proximate Component	Content in <i>P. ostreatus</i>
Moisture content (%)	17.54
Ash content (%)	10.82
Fats content (%)	0.097
Crude fibre content (%)	37.02
Protein content (%)	31.15
Carbohydrate content (NFE) (%)	3.373
Carbohydrate content using Anthrone Method (g/100g)	2.575

Values are expressed as percentages (%) except for carbohydrate content using the Anthrone method, which is expressed in g/100 g.

3.3. GC-MS Profile of Bioactive Constituents in *Pleurotus ostreatus*

Table 4 describes the GC-MS profile obtained for the ethanolic extract of *Pleurotus ostreatus*, outlining the bioactive constituents identified together with their peak numbers, molecular formulae, retention times and molecular masses. The chromatogram (Figure 1) displays twenty-nine distinct peaks, with retention times extending from 3.248 to 19.155 minutes. Compounds with large peak areas included 2(5H)-Furanone, 3-methyl- (Peak 1, 13.47%), Bromoacetic acid, octadecyl ester (Peak 3, 9.70%), L-Arabinitol (Peak 10, 13.00%), Didodecyl phthalate (Peak 21, 5.98%) and 9,17-Octadecadienal, (Z)- (Peak 25, 6.76%).

Table 4: GC–MS Profile of the Ethanolic Extract of *Pleurotus ostreatus* listing each detected compound together with its retention time, molecular formula and molecular weight.

Peak No.	Compounds Name	Peak Area %	Retenti on Time	Molecular Formula	Molecular Weight (m/z)	Structure
1	2(5H)-Furanone,3-methyl-	13.47	3.248	C ₅ H ₆ O ₂	98	
2	1,2,3,4-Butanetetrol, [S-(R*,R*)]- (1-Threitol)	2.80	3.528	C ₄ H ₁₀ O ₄	122	
3	Bromoacetic acid, octadecyl ester	9.70	3.665	<u>C₂₀H₃₉BrO₂</u>	391	
4	Ethene, 1,1-dichloro-	2.25	3.774	C ₂ H ₂ Cl ₂	97	
5	2-Hydroxyethyl butyl sulfide	2.44	3.848	C ₆ H ₁₄ OS	134	
6	Xylitol	1.13	3.940	<u>C₅H₁₂O₅</u>	152	
7	Methanamine, N-methoxy-	0.95	4.049	C ₂ H ₇ NO	61	
8	2-Hydroxyethyl butyl sulfide	2.26	4.106	C ₆ H ₁₄ OS	134	
9.	L-Arabinitol	1.20	4.220	<u>C₅H₁₂O₅</u>	152	
10.	L-Arabinitol	13.00	4.272	<u>C₅H₁₂O₅</u>	152	

Peak No.	Compounds Name	Peak Area %	Retenti on Time	Molecular Formula	Molecular Weight (m/z)	Structure
11.	1,2,3,4-Butanetetrol, [S-(R*,R*)]-	3.49	4.403	C ₄ H ₁₀ O ₄	122	
12.	Ethylene, 1,2-dichloro-, (Z)-	2.43	4.495	C ₂ H ₂ Cl ₂	97	
13.	Benzoic acid, methyl ester	2.29	4.621	C ₈ H ₈ O ₂	136	
14.	1H-Pyrazole, 4,5-dihydro-5,5-dimethyl-4-isopropylidene	2.85	4.987	<u>C₈H₁₄N₂</u>	138	
15.	Methyl salicylate	2.16	5.920	C ₈ H ₈ O ₃	152	
16.	Heptane, 2,3-dimethyl-	1.89	7.860	C ₉ H ₂₀	128	
17.	3-Isopropyl-5-methylhexan-2-one	1.63	7.905	C ₁₀ H ₂₀ O	156	
18.	1-Iodo-2-methylnonane	1.74	8.163	C ₁₀ H ₂₁ I	268	
19.	Tridecanal	1.73	11.390	<u>C₁₃H₂₆O</u>	198	$\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_{10}\text{CH}_2\text{CHO}$
20.	Hexadecanoic acid, methyl ester	2.22	13.221	C ₁₇ H ₃₄ O ₂	270	
21.	Didodecyl phthalate	5.98	13.599	C ₃₂ H ₅₄ O ₄	503	

Peak No.	Compounds Name	Peak Area %	Retenti on Time	Molecular Formula	Molecular Weight (m/z)	Structure
22.	9,12-Octadecadienoic acid (Z,Z)-,methyl ester	3.21	14.589	C ₁₉ H ₃₄ O ₂	294	 (CH ₂) ₉ COOH
23.	cis-Vaccenic acid	2.15	14.623	C ₁₈ H ₃₄ O ₂	282	 (CH ₂) ₅ CH ₃
24.	N-Methyladrenalin e, 3TMS derivative (metanephrine)	1.01	14.795	C ₁₈ H ₂₅ NO ₃ Si ₃	396	
25.	9,17-Octadecadienal, (Z)-	6.76	14.972	C ₁₈ H ₃₂ O	264	
26.	(R)-(-)-14-Methyl-8-hexadecyn-1-ol	0.96	16.425	C ₁₇ H ₃₂ O	252	
27.	Bicyclo[10.8.0]eicosane, cis-	3.35	17.484	C ₂₀ H ₃₈	278	
28.	16-Heptadecenal	1.37	18.812	C ₁₇ H ₃₂ O	252	
29.	Phthalic acid, monodecyl ester	3.58	19.155	C ₁₈ H ₂₆ O ₄	306	

Figure 1 :GC–MS chromatogram of the ethanolic extract of *Pleurotus ostreatus*.

4.0. Discussion

The phytochemical findings from this study suggest that *Pleurotus ostreatus* contains a broad spectrum of bioactive constituents that may offer health-promoting and therapeutic benefits [19]. The detection of alkaloids, flavonoids, phenolic compounds, tannins, saponins, terpenoids, steroids and cardiac glycosides suggest possible biological activities that highlight its nutritional and medicinal significance [20]. Extensive research has shown that alkaloids and flavonoids exhibit a wide range of pharmacological properties, most notably strong antioxidant, antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory activities [21;22]. These bioactive compounds may contribute importantly to reducing oxidative stress, suppressing pathogenic microbes and influencing inflammatory signaling pathways [22]. Such properties significantly contribute to the overall medicinal potential of *Pleurotus ostreatus* extracts. Alkaloids, in particular, have been associated with the inhibition of free radical formation and the modulation of various biochemical processes linked to disease prevention, while flavonoids are known to protect cellular components from oxidative damage and to enhance immune system function [23;24]. The

high abundance of saponins, suggested a broad range of therapeutic effects, including immunostimulatory activity, cholesterol-lowering capacity, and anticancer potential [20]. The cytotoxic and antiproliferative properties of saponins against cancerous cells show their value in chemopreventive and therapeutic applications [25]. The co-occurrence of this phytochemical group suggests possible synergistic interactions that amplify their individual bioactivities that may underlie the functional versatility of *P. ostreatus*, enabling it to exert multiple health-promoting effects simultaneously [20].

The proximate composition from this study demonstrated that *Pleurotus ostreatus* is not only medicinally valuable but also nutritionally significant [26]. Its high protein and crude fiber contents strengthen its role as a functional food capable of supplementing dietary protein intake while aiding digestion and bowel health [27]. Additionally, the low fat content aligns with the desirable characteristics of a healthy food source, suitable for individuals seeking low-calorie diets [28]. The ash content reflects the mineral richness of the mushroom, which may contribute essential

micronutrients for metabolic processes [27]. These support the suitability of *P. ostreatus* as a sustainable food component that combines nutritional adequacy with bioactive benefits.

The identification of major constituents such as 2(5H)-Furanone, 3-methyl-, L-arabinitol; Bromoacetic acid, octadecyl ester; 9,17-Octadecadienal (Z)-; and Didodecyl phthalate through GC-MS analysis indicated the presence of compounds with recognized biological activities [25]. Furanone derivatives are associated with antimicrobial and quorum-sensing inhibitory effects, while fatty acid esters such as octadecadienal derivatives and phthalates have been linked to antioxidant and cytoprotective functions[29]. The detection of L-arabinitol, a polyol commonly found in fungi, referenced its possible role as an osmoprotectant and metabolic intermediate, while also suggesting potential prebiotic or functional food relevance due to its low-caloric nature [30]. The identification of fatty acid-derived compounds such as 9,17-Octadecadienal (Z)- and Bromoacetic acid, octadecyl ester further supports the presence of lipophilic metabolites with reported antioxidant, antimicrobial, and cytoprotective activities [25]. Likewise, the presence of Didodecyl phthalate aligns with findings that organism-derived phthalate analogues can display antibacterial, cytoprotective, and antioxidant properties [31]. The coexistence of these bioactive molecules suggests an interplay of metabolites that may act synergistically to enhance the overall therapeutic efficacy of the mushroom extract [32]. Moreover, the diversity of identified metabolites demonstrates that *P. ostreatus* synthesizes a wide range of secondary metabolites in response to its ecological environment, contributing to its resilience and medicinal value [33]. Moreover, the diversity of identified metabolites supports the hypothesis that *P. ostreatus* synthesizes a wide range of secondary metabolites in response to its ecological environment, contributing to its resilience and medicinal value.

5.0. Conclusion and Recommendation

This study demonstrated that *Pleurotus ostreatus* possesses a rich phytochemical and nutritional composition, making it both a valuable dietary component and a potential source of natural therapeutic agents. The presence of saponins, alkaloids, phenols, and flavonoids, alongside GC-MS-identified compounds, reflects broad pharmacological potential, including antioxidant and

antimicrobial properties. High protein and fiber contents further enhance its nutritional value, while its low lipid content supports its suitability for health-conscious diets. Overall, *P. ostreatus* can be regarded as a multifunctional mushroom species with significant prospects for application in nutraceutical and pharmaceutical formulations. Further studies is required to investigate the specific pathways for the numerous therapeutic activities of the observed phytochemicals and GC-MS identified compounds.

6.0. References

- [1]. Berger RG, Bordewick S, Krahe NK, Ersoy F. Mycelium vs. Fruiting Bodies of Edible Fungi- A Comparison of Metabolites. *Microorganisms*, 2022; 10(7), 1379.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms10071379>
- [2]. Nsoh SV, Tacham WN, Ngwang MV, Kinge TR. The effect of substrates on the growth, yield, nutritional and phytochemical components of *Pleurotus ostreatus* supplemented with four medicinal plants. *Afr.J.Biotechnol.*,2022; 21(6), 292–304.
<https://doi.org/10.5897/ajb2022.17466>
- [3]. Bellettini MB, Fiorda FA, Maieves HA, Teixeira GL, Ávila S, Hornung PS, Júnior AM, Ribani RH. Factors affecting mushroom *Pleurotus* spp. *Saudi J. Biol. Sci.*,2019; 26(4), 633–646.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sjbs.2016.12.005>
- [4]. Carrasco J, Zied DC, Pardo JE, Preston GM, Pardo-Giménez A. Supplementation in mushroom crops and its impact on yield and quality. *AMB Express*, 2018; 8(1), 146.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13568-018-0678-0>
- [5]. Dimopoulou M, Chinou I, Gortzi O. A Systematic Review of the Seven Most Cultivated Mushrooms: Production Processes, Nutritional Value, Bioactive Properties and Impact on Non-Communicable Diseases. *Agriculture*, 2025; 15(13), 1329.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture15131329>
- [6]. Melanouri EM, Diamantis I, Dedousi M, Dalaka E, Antonopoulou P, Papanikolaou S, Politis I, Theodorou G, Diamantopoulou P. *Pleurotus ostreatus*: Nutritional Enhancement and Antioxidant Activity Improvement Through Cultivation on Spent Mushroom Substrate and Roots of Leafy Vegetables. *Fermentation*, 2025; 11(1), 20.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/fermentation11010020>

- [7]. Agunloye OM. Effect of aqueous extracts of *Pleurotus ostreatus* and *Lentinus subnudus* on activity of adenosine deaminase, arginase, cholinergic enzyme, and angiotensin-1-converting enzyme. *J. Food Biochem*, 2021; 45(3), e13490.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/jfbc.13490>
- [8]. Dicks L, Ellinger S. Effect of the Intake of Oyster Mushrooms (*Pleurotus ostreatus*) on Cardiometabolic Parameters-A Systematic Review of Clinical Trials. *Nutrients*, 2020; 12(4), 1134.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/nu12041134>
- [9]. Zhou Y, Chu M, Ahmadi F, Agar OT, Barrow CJ, Dunshea FR, Suleria HR. A comprehensive review on phytochemical profiling in mushrooms: Occurrence, biological activities, applications and future prospective. *Food Rev. Int*, 2024; 40(3), 924–951.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/87559129.2023.2202738>
- [10]. Fiehn O. Metabolomics by Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry: Combined Targeted and Untargeted Profiling. *Curr. Protoc. Mol. Biol*, 2016; 114, 30.4.1–30.4.32.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/0471142727.mb3004s114>
- [11]. Hamad D, El-Sayed H, Ahmed W, Sonbol H, Ramadan AH. GC-MS Analysis of Potentially Volatile Compounds of *Pleurotus ostreatus* Polar Extract: In vitro Antimicrobial, Cytotoxic, Immunomodulatory, and Antioxidant Activities. *Front. Microbiol.*, 2022; 13, 834525.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2022.834525>
- [12]. Olivia NU, Goodness UC, Obinna OM. Phytochemical profiling and GC-MS analysis of aqueous methanol fraction of *Hibiscus asper* leaves. *Futur. J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2021; 7, 59
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s43094-021-00208-4>
- [13]. Mlozi SH, Mmongoyo JA, Chacha M. GC-MS analysis of bioactive phytochemicals from methanolic leaf and root extracts of *Tephrosia vogelii*. *Scientific African*, 2022; Vol.16, e01255, ISSN 2468-2276,
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sciaf.2022.e01255>.
- [14]. Yogashree GD, ShivakumarP, Shrishail H. Phytochemical Screening and GC-MS Analysis of Root Extracts of *Parkia biglandulosa* (Wight&Arn.). *Plant Archives*. 2021; 21. 10.51470.
- [15]. Banu KS, Cathrine L. General techniques involved in phytochemical analysis. *Int. j. adv. res. chem. sci*, 2015; 2;(4);25-32.
- [16]. Bandiola TB. Extraction and qualitative phytochemical screening of medicinal plants: A brief summary. *International J. Pharm.* 2018; 8;(1);137-143.
- [17]. AOAC. Association of official analytical chemistry. *Methods of analysis*, Washington DC, 2044. 1970.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s13668-023-00468-x>
- [18]. Kareem KO, Holdbrooke S, Aina OO. et al. Phytochemical and GC-MS profiling of ethanol extract of African breadfruit (*Treculia africana* Decne) seeds. *Discov. Plants*, 2024; 1, 47.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s44372-024-00050-x>
- [19]. Mishra V, Tomar S, Yadav P, Vishwakarma S, Singh MP. Elemental Analysis, Phytochemical Screening and Evaluation of Antioxidant, Antibacterial and Anticancer Activity of *Pleurotus ostreatus* through In Vitro and In Silico Approaches. *Metabolites*, 2022; 12(9), 821.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/metabo12090821>
- [20]. Gashaw G, Getu A. Phytochemical Characteristics Evaluation of *Pleurotus* species Cultivated on Agricultural Wastes in Chiro, Ethiopia. *Indian J. Agric. Res.*, 2021; 55(3).
<https://doi.org/10.18805/IJARE.A-526>
- [21]. Othman L, Sleiman A, Abdel-Massih RM. Antimicrobial activity of polyphenols and alkaloids in middle eastern plants. *Front. Microbiol*, 2019; 10, 911.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2019.00911>
- [22]. Ullah A, Munir S, Badshah SL, Khan N, Ghani L, Poulson BG, Emwas AH, Jaremko M. Important Flavonoids and Their Role as a Therapeutic Agent. *Molecules* (Basel, Switzerland), 2020; 25(22), 5243.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules25225243>
- [23]. Macáková K, Afonso R, Saso L, Mladěnka P. The influence of alkaloids on oxidative stress and related signaling pathways. *Free Radic. Biol. Med.*, 2019; 134, 429–444.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.freeradbiomed.2019.01.026>
- [24]. Sireesha B, Reddy BV, Basha SK, Chandra K, Anasuya D. A review on pharmacological activities of alkaloids. *WJCMPr*, 2019; 01(06), 230–234.
<https://doi.org/10.37022/wjcmpr.2019.01068>
- [25]. Khan F, Magaji MG, Abdu-Aguye I, Hussaini IM, Hamza A, Olarukooba AB, Maje IM. Phytochemical profiling of the bioactive principles of *Alysicarpus glumaceus* (Vahl) DC. *Aerialparts. Istanbul J. Pharm*, 2021; 51(2), 228-

238. <https://doi.org/10.26650/IstanbulJPharm.2020.0071>
- [26]. Singh A, Saini RK, Kumar A, Chawla P, Kaushik R. Mushrooms as Nutritional Powerhouses: A Review of Their Bioactive Compounds, Health Benefits, and Value-Added Products. *Foods* (Basel, Switzerland), 2025; 14(5), 741. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods14050741>
- [27]. Effiong ME, Umeokwochi CP, Afolabi IS, Chinedu SN. Assessing the nutritional quality of *Pleurotus ostreatus* (oyster mushroom). *Front. Nutr.*, 2023; 10, 1279208. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnut.2023.1279208>
- [28]. Dimopoulou M, Kolonas A, Mourtakos S, Androutsos O, Gortzi O. Nutritional composition and biological properties of sixteen edible mushroom species. *Applied Sciences* (Basel, Switzerland), 2022; 12(16), 8074. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app12168074>
- [29]. Sharafutdinov IS, Trizna EY, Baidamshina DR, Ryzhikova MN, Sibgatullina RR, Khabibrakhmanova AM, Latypova LZ, Kurbangalieva AR, Rozhina EV, Klinger-Strobel M, Fakhrullin RF, Pletz MW, Bogachev MI, Kayumov AR, Makarewicz O.. Antimicrobial effects of sulfonyl derivative of 2(5H)-furanone against planktonic and biofilm associated methicillin-resistant and -susceptible *S. aureus*. *Front. Microbiol.*, 2017; 8, 2246. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2017.02246>
- [30]. Meng J, Mäkelä MR, de Vries RP. Identification of an l-arabitol transporter from *Aspergillus niger*. *Biomolecules*, 2023; 13(2), 188. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biom13020188>
- [31]. Huang L, Zhu X, Zhou S, Cheng Z, Shi K, Zhang C, Shao H. Phthalic Acid Esters: Natural Sources and Biological Activities. *Toxins*, 2021; 13(7), 495. <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxins13070495>
- [32]. Wadhwa K, Kapoor N, Kaur H, Abu-Seer EA., Tariq M, Siddiqui S, Yadav VK, Niazi P, Kumar P, Alghamdi S. A comprehensive review of the diversity of fungal secondary metabolites and their emerging applications in healthcare and environment. *Mycobiology*, 2024; 52(6), 335–387. <https://doi.org/10.1080/12298093.2024.2416736>
- [33]. Adeoye-Isijola, M.O., Jonathan, S.G., Coopoosamy, R.M. et al. Molecular characterization, gas chromatography mass spectrometry analysis, phytochemical screening and insecticidal activities of ethanol extract of *Lentinus squarrosulus* against *Aedes aegypti* (Linnaeus). *Mol Biol Rep* ., 2021; 48, 41–55. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11033-020-06119-6>.

BY

Copyright © 2025 by the authors. This article is an open access article under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits use, distribution and reproduction in other forums is permitted, provided the original author(s) and the copyright owner(s) are credited and that the original publication in this journal is cited, in accordance with accepted academic practice.